

Prediction of Glass Cartridge Robustness in Assembly line Loading

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Scope

Our drug contained cartridges must be able to withstand both:

- Component handling on the assembly line.
- Device assembly loading.
- In-use loading (general user handling).
- Loading relating to foreseeable misuse (drop, bending etc.).

Scope of this investigation

Thus a safety margin towards failure must be quantified

A Traditional Approach to Structural Robustness

Case: Circular steel rod of diameter d in tension

The constant axial force F is a design specification

The design stress can be calculated as:

$$\sigma_{nominal} = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{4F}{\pi d^2}$$

The failure criterion, σ_{yield} is typically a minimal value supplied by the material vendor.

The safety factor must then only account for the diameter tolerance:

$$Sf = \frac{\sigma_{yield}}{\sigma_{nominal}}$$

Now – What if....

Multiple forces F_1 , F_2 , F_3 are varying and dependant on:

- Interfacing component geometry
- Variation having different distributions
- Assembly equipment settings

The failure criterion is not well established and dependant on both material properties and processing.

The design stress depends on the rate of the loading: $F(t)$.

Then...

The safety factor can neither be calculated from nominal dimensions nor be based on a worst case scenario!

Introduction: Final Assembly of a disposable Insulin pen

Introduction: The assembly rig

Introduction: How is the Cartridge loaded?

Component section view

Stress view from Explicit FE-model

Cartridge

Introduction: How is the Cartridge loaded?

Component section view

Stress view

Interfacing thermoplastic part with 4 deformation ribs which support the cartridge

Introduction: How is the Cartridge loaded?

- Elastic-plastic deformation of the ribs cause bending stresses in the cartridge
- The rotational orientation of the cartridge can be regarded random

Rib axial section stress view

Procedure for Determining the Safety Factor

- Determine the nominal cartridge loading from the interfacing component.
- Choose the predominant dimensions and the corresponding tolerances that influence the loading.
- Set up a virtual model based Design of Experiments study (DoE) having a number of selected combination of parameter values.
- Run FE-analyses on the 10 sets.
- Run a DoE based on these combinations to evaluate parameter sensitivity and distribution of the applied stress.
- Determine the stress based strength of the cartridges and its distribution.
- Calculate the statistical based safety factor.

series	Pattern	Nut Thickness	Nut Radius	Cartridge	Nut-Cartridge Position
1	----	0,3	4,97	9,15	0,18
2	1111	0,3	4,97	9,15	0,18
3	-000	0,3	5,1	9,25	0,59
4	-+++	0,3	5,22	9,35	1
5	0-0+	0,35	4,97	9,25	1
6	00+-	0,35	5,1	9,35	0,18
7	0+-0	0,35	5,22	9,15	0,59
8	+-+0	0,4	4,97	9,35	0,59
9	+0-+	0,4	5,1	9,15	1
10	++0-	0,4	5,22	9,25	0,18

The Nature of the Rib Deformation Response

- Typical stress/strain behavior of an amorphous thermoplastic is highly non-linear and rate dependent:

Stress response for three different loading rates

Dynamic Explicit FE-analysis model

- Reduced model including only relevant components.
- The model takes rate dependency of the materials into account.
- The short duration of the assembly can be simulated in real time.

The Cartridge is pushed into engagement using forced displacement

Guiding dimensions

Pos	Parameter (type)	Expected distribution
D ₁	Deformation rib thickness (dimension)	Normal
D ₂	Deformation rib distance to centre line (dimension)	Normal
D ₃	Cartridge to rib axial penetration (displacement)	Normal
D ₄	Cartridge outer diameter (dimension)	Normal
D ₅	Cartridge rotation relative to deformation ribs (angle)	Stochastic

FE-analyses

- 10 analyses were ran with different geometry/position combinations of D_1 to D_4 having applied stress as the output parameter.
- Remark that this is not a full factorial EoD – rather a preliminary study.

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Outer rim tensile stress
(output parameter)

Max Tensile Stress Comparison

Thin rib with largest nut rib diameter combined with small diameter cartridge

S, Max. Principal
SNEG, (fraction = -1.0)
(Avg: 70%)

All nominal dimensions

S, Max. Principal
SNEG, (fraction = -1.0)
(Avg: 75%)

Thick rib with narrow nut rib diameter combined with large diameter cartridge

= Worst Case

S, Max. Principal
SNEG, (fraction = -1.0)
(Avg: 75%)

When does glass fail?

Prerequisites:

- Tensile stresses are present and critical for onset of cracking.
- In the stressed area imperfections are present
 - Small imperfections such as micro-cracks are inevitable in all practical glass samples especially on their outside surfaces
- The stress level and the size of the defect is such that the Griffith criterion is met -> brittle fracture.

$$\sigma_f * \sqrt{a} \geq \sqrt{\frac{2 * E * \gamma}{\pi}}$$

Outer rim imperfection location

Failure Criterion of Glass – a Practical Approach

Approach:

- A uniform tensile hoop stress state obtained from internal pressure on the inside
- This will capture the strength of the weakest imperfection

- Length = 65 mm
- Outer Diameter = 11.3 mm

Burst Measurement of Glass Strength Variation

Failure limit vs. loading rate

- Furthermore the failure stress of glass is depending on the loading rate.
- The figure shows the probability of failure vs stress level for various loading rates, ranging from 0.01 MPa/s to 1000 MPa/s.
- This can be used to relate the failure stress levels of the slow burst measurements to the high loading rate in the assembly line.
- The strength amplification factor due to loading rate dependence:

$$S_{\alpha} = 1.15^{\log\left(\frac{v_{assembly}}{v_{burst-test}}\right)}$$

Fig. 12. Failure probability F of a predamaged surface for various rates of stress increase α . (predamaged area: 100 mm², grain size: 600)

First DoE analysis in JMP (statistical software)

- The purpose of the first narrow scoped analysis was to have an indication on the parameter sensitivity.
- The relative nut to cartridge axial position (D_3) had most impact on imposed stress variation.
- The DoE confirmed our assumption on worst case parameter combination.

Term	Estimate	Std Error	t Ratio	Prob> t
Nut-Cartridge Position	12,926829	2,496165	5,18	0,0066*
Nut Thickness	37,333333	20,46855	1,82	0,1422
Cartridge	-13,66667	10,23428	-1,34	0,2527
Nut Radius	7,4520256	8,185239	0,91	0,4141

Safety Margin Considerations

- No cartridge cracking is acceptable.
- What measure should be used for the distribution overlap (if it exists)?
- Could the glass strength distribution be more narrow if the process were altered?
- Are there any assembly settings that may limit the loading on the cartridge?

Preliminary Safety factor Calculation

- For this study, the highest imposed tensile hoop stress (Worst Case) out of the FE analysis is used as a preliminary measure.
- Taking the velocity dependence of the glass strength into account, the safety factor can then be calculated as:
 - $Sf = \frac{\textit{Lowest burst stress} \cdot \textit{strength amplification factor}}{\textit{Maximum imposed stress}}$

Further work

- The DoE should be full factorial (16 combinations or more).
- From these results a distribution should be fitted.
- A reasonable measure for distribution overlap (imposed cartridge stress vs. strength) must be agreed upon (e.g. ppm).

Conclusion

- Conventional calculation of Safety Factors is not suitable for non-linear load cases with many dependencies.
- Combining the virtual DoE with the experimentally determined glass strength provided:
 - Failure prevention for complex load cases in high volume production.
 - Ability to specify entities of the device design and assembly setup more precisely.
 - Improved the link between R&D and production in the device development.